

CANDLE

National CAncer data Node DeveLopErs

CANDLE is a Coordination and Support Action providing tools and support for Member States to set up National Cancer Data Nodes.

Concept

National Cancer Data Nodes (NCDN) are federated hubs for standardising and harmonising cancer data procedures within their country. CANDLE will support the development of NCDN by:

- conceptualising the nodes on different levels,
- identifying challenges and propose solutions aligned with the European Health Data Space,
- developing national implementation roadmaps,
- establishing a policy dialogue,
- fostering scale-up via a CANDLE Resource Kit and National Cancer Data Node Network.

Outcomes and Impact

- A CANDLE Resource Kit will provide essential tools for Member States,
- A Network of National Cancer Data Nodes will advance the dialogue beyond the project duration,
- Strong stakeholder engagement will ensure relevance to all relevant actors,
- Cancer researchers can access more data,
- This can fuel the development of new cancer treatments, diagnostics, and better information to patients, survivors, and carers – and much more,
- Thus, CANDLE will help Europe better understand cancer.

**REDUCE
THE BURDEN
OF CANCER
IN EUROPE**

Empower Europe's fight against cancer and join the CANDLE initiative!

Join the Stakeholder Engagement Group [↗](#)

Sign up to the CANDLE Newsletter [↗](#)

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 CANDLE Project

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Partners: 40 (31 beneficiaries, 9 affiliated partners)

Coordinator: Health-RI

Budget: €3M

Duration: June 2025 – May 2028

Research Infrastructures involved: ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, EIRENE, ECRIN, EuroBioimaging

Member States involved: 20

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